

EXPLORING THE RESILIENCE OF PRISONERS ENGAGED IN DISTANCE E-LEARNING: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The article investigates the experiences and resilience of prisoners pursuing formal education via remote e-learning in a Namibian jail. Twelve prisoners in all, registered and enrolled in classes to pursue official certifications while confined, were chosen to participate. Only prisoners who satisfied the requirements of formally being enrolled in educational programs were included, thanks to the sampling technique. To adequately document the participants' comments, the interviews were taped. An experienced English-speaking transcriber later wrote a full transcription of these recordings. The researcher then employed an interpretive paradigm to examine the transcribed data, which enabled a thorough comprehension of the participants' experiences and the difficulties they encounter. It was discovered that the resilience of imprisoned students stems from their significant dependence on drive, self-control, and other people's encouragement to achieve. Some highlight the value of peer pressure and self-encouragement, while others talk about the advantages and disadvantages of distant learning, especially regarding time management and technology access. For resilience prison students need to be taught self-regulatory skills; self-discipline and internal motivation; to pursue their studies despite the constraints of the prison environment; to possess a mindset that prioritizes personal growth, viewing their academic endeavors as a method to improve themselves and create opportunities for a more favorable future after release. Implications are the following: Correctional institutions should prioritize teaching self-regulation, self-discipline, and internal motivation as part of rehabilitation programs. Providing imprisoned students with tools to manage their emotions, set and pursue academic goals, and stay focused despite distractions can help them overcome the challenges they face in the prison environment. Peer mentoring programs and group study opportunities could foster an environment where students motivate each other and hold each other accountable for their progress. Method of instruction plays a critical role in the resilience of imprisoned students. While distance learning offers flexibility, the lack of reliable technology and proper time management skills can hinder its effectiveness. To address these challenges, prisons might need to invest in better technological infrastructure and training programs to equip students with the skills they need to succeed in remote education settings. Resilient imprisoned students tend to adopt a growth mindset that emphasizes personal development. Correctional education programs could reinforce this mindset by framing academic achievements not just as means for earning qualifications but as avenues for personal transformation and future opportunities. Educational programs in prisons should explicitly tie academic success to the potential for successful reintegration into society, such as through employment opportunities, vocational training, or continued education. The resilience of imprisoned students is influenced by both internal factors (drive, self-control) and external

factors (encouragement from others, peer pressure). This suggests a need for a comprehensive support system that includes not only educational staff but also counselors, mentors, and community programs.

KEYWORDS: Flexible, hardship, restrictions, student, resilience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prison environments that are restrictive, lack of direct assistance, and restricted access to resources are just a few of the challenges faced by incarcerated individuals who participate in formal education. Those that stick with their studies, though, show incredible fortitude. They adjust to these circumstances by cultivating a mindset that is centered on their own development and prospects being disciplined and mastering the art of time management. This resilience provides a road to a better future by assisting with their academic performance as well as their general recovery. The analysis of these students' experiences emphasizes the value of offering educational programs inside of jails and shows how education can change lives even in the most trying situations. [1] found that education is a project of freedom, and we must equip our students with the skills and knowledge to re-think, reimagine and challenge dominant systems of knowledge and power. Given that jailed students already confront difficulties in their academic careers, this shift has sparked worries about their resilience and mental health [2]. To promote the academic and personal well-being of prison students enrolled in distant education programs, it is imperative to comprehend the variables that contribute to their resilience.

In the context of education, the idea of resilience has drawn a lot of attention, especially in relation to helping students who are dealing with hardship or difficult situations. One group that exemplifies the need for resilience is students who are engaged in distant e-learning programs while incarcerated. The term "resilience" refers to the ability to effectively cope with major stressors or traumatic events, such as difficulties in relationships, severe health issues, or challenges in the employment and financial matters [3]. Resilience is crucial in the prison education setting to assist students in overcoming many challenges, such as limited access to resources, disruptions in their learning environment, and the psychological impact of being incarcerated [2].

Research has shown the importance of resilience for jailed students who are engaging in remote online learning courses. According to the study conducted by [4], incarcerated individuals who participated in distance learning programs shown increased resilience as they were able to pursue their studies despite the constraints of the prison environment. [5] found that the cultivation of resilience traits, including as self-control and problem-solving skills, had a vital role in the academic achievement of incarcerated students enrolled in distant education programs.

Moreover, research has established that social support plays a pivotal role in fostering resilience among incarcerated students participating in remote education programs. Tewksbury and Stengel (2006) emphasized the importance of establishing supportive relationships with external support networks, as well as inside the prison community, to assist incarcerated students in overcoming the challenges of distance learning. These support networks can provide motivation, guidance in

education, and psychological stability, all of which are essential for cultivating resilience [2]. Furthermore, it has been found that the flexibility and availability of remote e-learning programs improve the ability of incarcerated students to adapt and obtain education. [6] argue that the self-paced and self-directed nature of online education allows incarcerated students to tailor their training to their own needs and circumstances. This promotes a feeling of independence and the belief in one's ability to succeed, which are crucial elements of resilience. In order to achieve academic success and personal growth, prisoners engaging in remote e-learning programs must demonstrate resilience. Teachers and policymakers can create targeted interventions and support systems to improve the educational experiences and outcomes of jailed individuals by understanding the obstacles faced by this demographic and the essential components that foster their resilience.

1.1 Literature Review

Student disturbances occurring within correctional facilities have uncertain effects on the academic progress of these individuals. According to [7], higher education is crucial in improving the resilience of criminals by developing their coping abilities and fostering a sense of solidarity within the institution. Internal elements, such as resilience, can have an impact on the subjective well-being of students [8]. Resilience, in the context of prison education, pertains to the jailed students' capacity to adjust and flourish despite facing various challenges, including scarce resources, social isolation, and the psychological strain of imprisonment [9]. Research has indicated that some characteristics, including the availability of education, social support, and self-efficacy, can enhance the development of resilience in incarcerated individuals [10; 2]. The introduction of online learning throughout the epidemic has introduced intricacy to the educational encounters of jailed students.

Digital technologies enhance the acquisition of competencies vital for students' professional efficacy, encompassing problem-solving, conceptual framework development, and process comprehension [11]. That is why the limited availability of technology in prison might have an impact on the students' ability to cope with challenges and their psychological well-being. Nevertheless, a study indicates that incarcerated students can experience more autonomy, adaptability, and a sense of direction through online education, so bolstering their ability to recover from adversity [12].

It is important to recognize and analyze the determination of convicts in overcoming the substantial obstacles they encounter when pursuing an education. Resilience is the capacity to adjust and flourish in challenging situations, which is especially vital for those who are imprisoned because of the rigorous and frequently stressful prison setting [13]. The jailed students' capacity to surmount the multiple obstacles they encounter in their pursuit of education is a crucial component of their resilience. According to [2], incarceration can result in a sense of isolation and detachment from the larger educational community. Additionally, it has the potential to alter educational trajectories and restrict the availability of educational resources. Despite the hurdles they confront, a small number of prisoners show exceptional resilience by actively participating in educational programs and making use of the resources provided to them in order to attain their academic objectives. The study conducted by [14] discovered that individuals who engaged in educational programs demonstrated greater levels of institutional adaptation, vocational readiness, and self-worth, suggesting their resilience. According to the

study conducted by [4], incarcerated students who participated in educational activities exhibited improved behavior in comparison to their classmates who did not participate. This improvement was shown in a reduction in disciplinary infractions.

The resilience of detained students greatly depends on their capacity to keep a positive mindset and a firm sense of purpose despite facing challenging circumstances. Imprisonment can be a harrowing experience that triggers emotions such as melancholy, despair, and apathy [5]. Nevertheless, some incarcerated individuals possess a mindset that prioritizes personal growth, viewing their academic endeavors as a method to improve themselves and create opportunities for a more favorable future [15]. In a study conducted by [16], it was discovered that offenders who took part in educational programs had a higher probability of developing positive self-perception, expressing a clear sense of purpose, and showing a readiness to engage in activities that contribute to society after being released from prison. The results indicate that educational programs have the potential to strengthen the resilience of convicts and result in better outcomes. Prisons and educational institutions can bolster the resilience of jailed students by offering assistance and resources, in addition to their pre-existing resilience. Prisons can implement educational programs that are effective by integrating community-based learning, mentorship, and trauma-informed tactics. These programs have the potential to foster resilience and enhance academic achievement [2; 4].

The resilience of jailed students is an intricate and diverse concept that is impacted by a range of circumstances, including as institutional, societal, and individual qualities. Collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can lead to the development of equitable and effective educational opportunities for jailed children. This can be achieved by gaining insight into the characteristics that promote resilience in these students and implementing policies that improve their educational outcomes.

The adoption of learning management systems (LMS) and e-learning has been progressively prevalent in educational institutions. E-learning has acquired significant popularity due to its ability to improve educational outcomes and enhance the quality of the learning experience. E-learning is the process of sharing educational knowledge and content using digital technology [17]. One benefit of online learning is its capacity to offer readily available and adaptable learning possibilities. Students need the capability to conveniently access instructional resources using e-learning platforms like learning management systems (LMSs) [18]. This flexibility allows students to efficiently balance their academic endeavors with other facets of their lives, which is especially beneficial for persons who have conflicting obligations such as employment or familial duties. Moreover, it has been confirmed that e-learning improves learner motivation and involvement. By using interactive multimedia, gamification components, and personalized feedback, it is possible to create a more advanced and captivating learning environment [19]. Furthermore, regularly monitoring the advancement of students and offering prompt feedback would assist in maintaining students' interest and active participation in the educational process [17].

One additional benefit of e-learning is its ability to enhance the scalability and cost-efficiency of educational delivery. Institutions can increase their student enrollment by utilizing digital technology, hence eliminating the need for extra instructors or physical infrastructure [18]. For firms that provide online or distance learning programs, the ability to scale without being limited by the location of students can be especially beneficial. Nevertheless, there are obstacles that

need to be tackled prior to the effective implementation of e-learning and LMS in educational settings. The efficacy of e-learning programs can be influenced by various aspects, including the creation of relevant digital content, the presence of dependable internet access, and technological literacy [17]. Furthermore, institutions must give high importance to addressing student data security and privacy concerns while integrating e-learning platforms into their current educational systems and processes [18].

Modern education now integrates the use of learning management systems and e-learning. In order to achieve a successful and efficient incorporation of these technologies into their educational programs, institutions must confront the obstacles associated with implementation, despite the several advantages they provide, such as adaptability, involvement, and expandability.

1.2 Challenges associated with the use of e-learning and learning management systems in educational institutions

Technological literacy levels may affect the ability of students and faculty members to effectively use e-learning platforms and adapt to new technologies [17]. Dependable internet connectivity is crucial for the effectiveness of e-learning initiatives. Nevertheless, this could be a challenge in certain geographic regions or socioeconomic circumstances where availability of high-speed internet may be limited [18]. To guarantee that e-learning experiences are both effective and in line with learning objectives, institutions must provide resources to create captivating, interactive, and educationally sound digital content [18]. It is imperative to prioritize data privacy and security when using e-learning technologies and collecting student data. To address these challenges, institutions should implement suitable regulations and utilize technological protections [18]. Incorporating e-learning platforms into existing educational systems, such as student information systems and administrative processes, can pose challenges and require a significant amount of effort. Substantial coordination and technical knowledge are necessary [17].

Ensuring learner motivation and engagement in an e-learning environment can be more challenging than in traditional face-to-face settings. The absence of direct interpersonal interaction and the self-reliant nature of e-learning can result in less engagement and a greater proportion of students dropping out of their studies [18]. Faculty Adoption and Training: Effective implementation of e-learning programs necessitates faculty members who possess both the willingness and capability to embrace and use these technologies into their instructional approaches. To maximize the utilization of e-learning tools and overcome any reluctance to adapt, it is crucial to provide comprehensive training and assistance to faculty members [19]. To optimize the advantages of e-learning and learning management systems, educational institutions must efficiently address these problems and seamlessly incorporate them into the broader educational framework.

Research provides evidence for the advantages and characteristics of correctional education programs. Research has demonstrated that these programs have a significant impact on decreasing the likelihood of repeat offenses among those who are currently serving time in prison [20; 21; 22]. Engaging in educational programs while incarcerated has been linked to enhanced cognitive capacity, increased self-confidence, and greater emotional control among imprisoned students [23; 24; 25]. Moreover, incarcerated students can access valuable educational resources and enhance their abilities through the utilization of digital learning

platforms and restricted internet access within correctional facilities, which may not be accessible under different circumstances [21; 26]. Research has shown that giving prisoners the opportunity to use technology-based educational resources can enhance their ability to reintegrate into society after being released from prison [5; 22]. Studies suggest that giving educational programs, including digital learning opportunities, to jailed individuals can result in notable advantages such as decreased rates of reoffending, improved cognitive and emotional abilities, and better reintegration into society after release. Offering these opportunities is essential for promoting the rehabilitation and individual growth of incarcerated students.

1.3 Purpose

The purpose of this case study is to examine the resilience of jailed students who are participating in formal education through distance e-learning to adapt and recover from challenges. The study seeks to understand how incarcerated individuals in a correctional facility in Namibia are able to overcome the unique challenges of pursuing education while in prison. The research aims to examine the factors that contribute to the ongoing survival and success of individuals, offering understanding into the impact of education in promoting personal growth, rehabilitation, and the potential for positive life changes following incarceration.

1.4 Question

How do prison students demonstrate resilience while pursuing formal education through distance e-learning, and what factors contribute to their ability to overcome the challenges of studying in a correctional environment?

2. METHOD

2.1 Data collection

The study was conducted at a Namibian prison, focusing on 12 inmates pursuing degrees through distance education. Participants were carefully chosen based on their active enrollment in accredited educational programs, employing purposive sampling to gain insights from those experiencing remote learning in prison. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore their motivations, experiences, and challenges. These interviews were recorded with a tape recorder to capture all nuances of the discussions. The recordings were then transcribed and analyzed to identify key themes related to distance learning, ensuring an accurate representation of the participants' perspectives.

2.2 Data analysis

The data analysis began with the verbatim transcription of tape-recorded interviews, ensuring every word, pause, and expression was accurately captured. A skilled transcriber, fluent in English, handled this task, preserving the nuances and meanings in the participants' statements. By transcribing word for word, the transcriber maintained the authenticity of the participants' voices, capturing their true sentiments, emotions, and experiences. Once the transcriptions were complete, they were passed to the author for interpretive analysis. This method involved a

careful examination of the transcriptions to identify key themes, patterns, and insights related to the experiences of incarcerated students engaged in online learning. The interpretive approach was ideal for this study, allowing the author to delve into the personal and subjective meanings the participants attached to their educational experiences, uncovering the profound significance of their responses.

To enhance the reliability of the analysis, the author employed triangulation by comparing the interview results with existing research and scholarly literature. This process had multiple objectives: validating the findings by checking their consistency with existing knowledge, providing a broader context for understanding the participants' experiences, and highlighting unique aspects of resilience and adaptation specific to incarcerated learners in a distance education setting. By integrating various sources of information, the author gained a comprehensive understanding of how incarcerated students navigate the challenges of their learning environment. The use of existing literature in triangulation not only reinforced the study's findings but also deepened the analysis of their educational journeys. The resilience exhibited by these individuals, providing a more comprehensive and detailed analysis. This approach enabled the author to provide a comprehensive study that not only encompassed the real-life experiences of the participants but also placed those experiences within the wider context of remote education, incarceration, and personal resilience.

3. Findings

Participant 1 said, *“Perseverance managing your time”*.

Participant 2 said, *“Focus on what you have to study”*

Participant 3 said, *“you have to push yourself and that you can only do through proper time management”*.

Participant 4 said, *“I used my own strategies of self-encouragement and asking other colleagues to guide me. Self-discipline and self-motivation”*

Participant 5 said, *“The challenge is if you do not have the mode of studying because distance, e-learning study is offered mostly through using of electronic devices”*.

Participant 6 said, *“I use the strategy that normally one would concentrating on in an environment, in a correctional setup is mostly about the, it is more in reading, it is about reading and do more thorough research about it, those are the strategies that one is using”*.

Participant 7 said, *“Be alone, focus, read, research and put all those things together”*.

Participant 8 said, *“The, I think the biggest challenges that students can face it is from themselves, which you has to do with time management, if you are not self-disciplined as a student, to give yourself time to do go through your study material, to do your assignments and to attend to any online classes or instructions given by the lecturers then it will, that is the biggest challenge that students can face”*. The second challenge is if you do not have the mode of studying because distance, e-learning study is offered mostly through using of electronic devices.

Participant 9 said, *“It is about discipline, first of all and you have to discipline yourself because it is not easy to study from a distance mode. There are challenges and there are socio*

challenges, there are family issues as well, so you need to make time and effort and be diligent, I mean to study from a distance”.

Participant 10 said, *“By being self-disciplined, setting out the dates and times, setting out the timetable for when I should do my assignments, when I should do my tests, and being able to, just having a programme for myself, for my studies and when I will be able to do my assignments”.*

Participant 11 said, *“I manage to study because I have self-discipline, self-control and the goodness of it for me I was put in a single cell, since I started my studies, I was in a single cell, so I had enough time if we knock at three o’clock”.*

Participant 12 said, *“We need encouragement, we need full support of everybody and all stakeholders from the institutions, from the lecturers, family members and officers”.*

4. DISCUSSION

The study participants highlighted several essential factors that motivated them to pursue education through distance learning while in prison, as well as the challenges they faced in doing so. Despite encountering difficult circumstances, a number of individuals had a robust sense of optimism and determination to enhance their lives via education.

Participant 1 demonstrated their unwavering resolve to discover hope by dedicating themselves to the pursuit of knowledge. They recognized that the sole viable method of studying accessible to them in prison is through online learning. This illustrates a strong innate need to seek personal development through education, even in the face of constraints imposed by incarceration [14].

Participant 3 expressed a sense of admiration, stating, "I was motivated by witnessing numerous individuals who have effectively advanced from this circumstance." As a result, I made a firm decision to imitate their behavior, guaranteeing that whenever I am released from prison, I will take on the burden of supporting my family without relying on anyone. The individual in question was motivated by external influences and a great desire to support their family upon their release. The statement highlights the importance of social support and long-term goals in sustaining educational pursuits [4].

The participants also discussed the challenges they faced, such as the need for self-discipline, effective time management, and access to technology. Participant 8 emphasized that the primary challenges faced by students are self-imposed, particularly in relation to time management. Insufficient self-discipline among students might hinder their ability to effectively manage their time for studying, completing assignments, attending online lectures, and following instructions from their lecturers. This is recognized as the main obstacle that students may encounter. This highlights the importance of developing strong self-regulatory skills when engaging in remote learning, particularly in the setting of being in prison [27].

Participant 5 highlighted the arduousness of acquiring the necessary equipment, stating, "The obstacle lies in the lack of resources for remote learning, as e-learning predominantly depends on the utilization of electronic devices." This underscores the imperative for correctional facilities to provide enough technological resources and support to incarcerated individuals who are participating in remote education [28].

Overall, the participants' experiences highlight the importance of determination and ambition in pursuing educational objectives while incarcerated. Additionally, they emphasize the significance of institutional support and individual self-management skills in successfully overcoming the unique obstacles of this context.

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE AND POLICY

The results of this study will enhance our comprehension of how incarcerated students might cultivate and sustain resilience while facing the difficulties of remote e-learning. The findings will have practical implications for educational administrators, instructors, and support staff who work with incarcerated populations. This will allow them to effectively implement specific interventions and support systems to promote the resilience and well-being of prison students in the distance learning setting. The results of this study indicate many significant consequences for policy and implementation in the context of distant education in correctional facilities:

Given that distant learning frequently depends on electronic devices, it is imperative for prisons to emphasize the provision of secure and sufficient access to these technologies. One such approach is to allocate resources towards e-learning platforms, equip inmates with essential devices such as tablets or PCs, and establish a reliable internet connection where possible. The necessity of self-discipline and motivation among prisoners underscores the significance of well-organized support services. Prisons should implement mentorship programs in which seasoned or driven offenders can provide guidance to others, supplemented by periodic check-ins by educators or support personnel to assist inmates in maintaining their progress. It is imperative that distance learning programs provide the necessary adaptability to cater to the specific timetables and situations of incarcerated individuals. This encompasses providing self-paced classes and granting offenders the opportunity to advance at their own speed, which is vital in sustaining their motivation and involvement. Correctional officials and staff should get training to assist offenders in their educational pursuits, acknowledging the importance of education in the process of rehabilitation and reintegration. Their participation may encompass facilitating access to study materials, providing support, and establishing a favorable learning environment. Given that time management has been recognized as a major obstacle, it would be advantageous to offer inmates training on properly managing their time, specifically in juggling scholastic obligations with other responsibilities at the prison. Participants emphasized the significance of external assistance, indicating that policies should promote family engagement in the educational process. This may involve facilitating opportunities for family members to engage in educational milestones or offering updates on the inmate's progress, so strengthening their drive. It is important to customize educational programs to address the unique requirements and preferences of jailed individuals, with a potential emphasis on acquiring skills that will facilitate their reintegration into society and enable them to find job after their release. This can be accomplished by forming alliances with educational institutions and employers to guarantee the pertinence and practicality of the curriculum.

6. CONCLUSION

The study participants provide comprehensive and intricate insights into the motivations and challenges of engaging in distance learning while incarcerated, revealing a complex interplay between personal motivation, external support, and the constraints imposed by the prison environment. The participants' experiences revolve around the vital importance of self-discipline and internal motivation. Without external supervision, incarcerated individuals must heavily rely on self-regulation in order to achieve educational success. The participants were discussing the significance of maintaining a strong personal drive, setting goals, and adhering to schedules in order to stay focused. This self-discipline involves a broader range of skills and practices beyond simply managing time efficiently. Additionally, it entails sustaining motivation despite isolation, limited resources, and the difficulties associated with being confined. Many participants believe that education provides them and their family with better opportunities. They expect that acquiring a qualification will enhance their prospects of effective reintegration and improve their chances of securing employment upon release. The participants' educational experiences were significantly impacted and transformed by the influence and support networks provided by their peers. Several individuals noticed that seeing their fellow prisoners actively engaging in remote education motivated them to do the same, creating a positive circle of support that fosters a culture of learning within the jail. The participants emphasized the importance of receiving guidance from peers who have more skill or understanding in specific areas. This often compensates for the lack of direct interaction with instructors or access to instructional materials.

However, the challenges of participating in distant education while in a prison setting were freely acknowledged. Efficient time management was a critical concern due to the difficulty of balancing academic endeavors with other obligations in the unpredictable prison environment. The lack of private study spaces and limited availability of essential technologies such as electronic devices and internet access presented significant obstacles. The limitations hindered the participants' ability to fully participate in their courses and disrupted their learning process. Despite these challenges, the responses from the participants highlighted the remarkable ability of remote learning to create substantial transformations. Education not only provides essential skills and information for life after release, but also fosters a sense of purpose and direction that is crucial for rehabilitation. Moreover, granting convicts with academic qualifications can diminish the likelihood of reoffending by augmenting their employment prospects. The prospect of assuming the primary financial responsibility for their families upon release served as a compelling motivation for numerous volunteers.

In summary, while remote learning in prison presents challenges, it also offers a vital opportunity for personal development and long-lasting stability. The participants' experiences underscore the importance of self-discipline, peer support, and technological availability in surmounting educational challenges. This illustrates that with ample assistance and resources, remote education may have a significant impact on jailed individuals, empowering them to foresee and pursue a more advantageous future.

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